

ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES STUDENT'S PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Technology has definitely become the headline of the century. Every field of life, starting up with medicine, science, engineering, etc., and ending with education, goes hand in hand with technology and its development. It is undeniable that information and communication technology (ICT) has a significant impact on people's lives and the way they communicate.

But what is technology's impact on education?

Previously, there were only 4 main elements during the learning process: the student, the teacher, the book, and the blackboard. Learning was explained only through books, papers, notebooks, and pencils.

However, the last century has undergone tremendous changes due to technology, which has now become an integral and essential part of the teaching and learning process. The technological infrastructure in the learning process is translated into devices that serve to exchange information, process it, analyze it, etc.

The main purpose of technology in education is to increase the student's ability to concentrate, to be more creative, and to facilitate the learning and teaching process while increasing its efficiency. Students have grown responsible for their own learning through searching and finding (at least) information on the Internet and other technological tools, communicating and collaborating with each other, by encouraging independent learning among students.

Regarding learning a foreign language for specific reasons, and the impact of technology on it, a study was conducted in the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering where the familiarity of students with ESP and with technology during the ESP course was revealed.

The research concluded that students of Mechanical Engineering deal with technology in the classroom and take the best out of it, however, there is a lack of tools limiting them just to laptops or students' own personal smartphones, and rarely video projectors.

Students make use mostly of online dictionaries and mobile phone learning technology by using WhatsApp and other social media applications.

Keywords: ESP, technology, Mechanical Engineering, teaching, learning

Introduction

With technology revolutionizing our life in all its dimensions, it has become a target of endless studies.

Previous work

Countless number of studies have been conducted on technology and its role in education worldwide. As Albanian is concerned, there have been conducted studies related to Language for Specific Purposes, ESP in Mechanical Engineering, especially papers related to mechanical terminology, but there are no studies conducted dealing with the impact of technology on ESP learning and teaching in the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, PUT.

This paper has two main parts. The theoretical part is where data pertaining to ESP and technology, is collected and analyzed. The descriptive part: the term descriptive research refers to research questions, the design of the study, and data analysis conducted on that topic. We call it an observational research method because none of the research study variables are influenced in any capacity.

The paper attempts to:

1. Gather, describe and analyze data concerning ESP and Technology in general, mainly of the last years
2. Better target and evaluate our ESP Mechanical Engineering students' familiarity with ESP, their needs and requirements and to reveal what technological tools are actually used and which of digital technologies serve the common purpose of teachers which, in this context, is employing and applying effective teaching strategies involving technology by promoting effective learning.

1. Literature Review.

1.1 Technology and its impact on our life

Technology has become an inseparable part of our everyday life by walking hand in hand with us in our countless everyday activities, by undoubtedly revolutionizing our lives.

Almost, each of us starts the day by strongly embracing technology. We wake up and if not, mobile

phones or the so-called smartphones are “the first person to give the morning kiss”, and move on with the television, computer, etc. There are high-tech tools that actually monitor everything, starting with the daily steps one makes, measurement of blood pressure, or even home robots.

Then you move on to work, go out with friends, play with your kids...technology is there, everywhere. Beyond the shadow of a doubt, inventors that belong to the digital space and technology are actually scrambling to find ways to promote their platforms or tools to each member of society, be it kids or elderly people.

Technology was meant to help people, to make our lives easier, it was meant to serve us, right? But, when people fail to use technology and take the best out of it, what happens? What happens is that technology, manages to make us its servants and “it” the master.

In my opinion, somehow, sometimes we have come to be manipulated by technology, which is actually directing our lives. When people get addicted to smartphones, video games, YouTube videos, etc., it means that it is technology that is setting the priorities of each of us, it is technology that dominates our lives and our time.

But, in spite of what we mentioned earlier, no one ever can deny that technology has really enhanced our way of living and experiencing life.

It affects in many different fields of life, such as the healthcare industry, science, communication, and many others by ending up, with what concerns our work, and education. The healthcare industry of course has undergone substantial changes, which no one could have ever foreseen. Many chronic diagnoses such as hypertension, before would be considered life-threatening, nowadays with the big impact of technology, modern medicine has created the right tools to manage these health conditions, by improving life and increasing the lifespan of human beings.

Communication has changed a lot due to technology's advancement. We all know that initially, it was the telegraph the first technological tool of communication which then paved the way for the telephone, but now it is the internet cell phones and emails which are at the summit of most preferred methods of communication.

1.1.2 Technology in education and its role in this area of life.

There are three main components of technology in education (Burgin, M 1999)¹²: 1) organization and management of some educational system (from a school to the system of education of the whole country); 2) satisfaction of some supplementary needs of education systems and educators (e.g., information supply, communication facilities, word processing, etc.); 3) realization of a teaching/learning process. The latter type is called educational technology. It has three aspects.

First, the most obvious one is technology as a discipline for teaching and learning. The second aspect is the technology of learning, and the third one is the technology of teaching. Technologies of both latter types are called instructional or pedagogical technologies.

1.1.3 Definitions of Technology

Technology is the social phenomenon of the last 21st century, and no one can deny it, that being the case, as far as education is concerned, in order to have a very efficient usage of technology in this field, we have to really understand what technology stand for as a social phenomenon. But first, let us give some definitions regarding technology:

1. Technology is any systematized practical knowledge, based on experimentation and/or scientific theory, that enhances the capacity of society to produce goods and services, and which is embodied in productive skills, organization, or machinery.³

2. Technology is :

- a technical language;
- the science of the application of knowledge to practical purposes
- application of scientific knowledge to practical purposes.⁴

Apart from the above-mentioned, we put an emphasis on the influence it has on almost every aspect of life.

1.1.4 Technological approach to education

When it comes to the technological approach in education, the first thing that goes through one's head is, the presence of technological tools in the classroom, such as computers, video-projectors, internet connection, and why not smartphones. But of course, even advanced technological tools in different laboratories according to the study programs. All these means, serve the purpose of having a high diversity of methodologies and techniques being used during the teaching and learning process as well. It has facilitated the whole process of teaching and learning. Teachers have endless methods and techniques to implement in the classroom, and out of it. Students on the other side, have options on how to deepen their knowledge or understanding of a specific subject. There is always room for more wisdom in people's brains, and technology offers enormous sources where one can always learn something new. But, what I want to emphasize is the fact that technology should not act as a means that causes a metamorphosis in the teachers' role, by making it the main instrument and fading the role of the teacher which is, well teaching itself.

1.4.1 What is teaching?

As for what does teaching mean, many scholars have given their own definitions of what teaching is. “Teaching is intimate contact between a more mature personality and a less mature one which designed to further the education of the latter”.⁵ Morrison (1934), Dewey (1934) expressed this concept of teaching by an

1.¹ Technology in Education Mark Burgin

2. ³Pacey, A., "The Culture of Technology", 1983

3. ⁴ McGraw-Hill Concise Encyclopedia of Science and Technology. - New York - London - Tokyo, 1989

4. ⁵ H C Morrison (1934), retrieved from <https://worldcat.org/identities/lccn-no96056165/>

equation. "Teaching is learning as selling is to buying".⁶ According to John Brubacher (1939), "Teaching is arrangement and manipulation of a situation in which there are gaps or obstructions which an individual will seek to overcome and from which he will learn in the course of doing so".⁷ B.O. Smith defined teaching as "Teaching is a system of actions intended to induce learning"⁸. In the words of Gage (1963), "Teaching is a form of interpersonal influence aimed at changing the behavior potential of another person".⁹ Edmund Amidon (1967) defined teaching as "an interactive process, primarily involving classroom talk which takes place between teacher and pupil and occurs during certain definable activities"¹⁰. Many confuse teaching with training or indoctrination, well there's merely some resemblance among them. Teaching is not just meant only to teach and therefore has an effect on students' learning, it is also about face-to-face communication. Understanding student's needs and trying to find a way to fulfill them. It is not just as Smith in 1963 who gave an extended definition of teaching said, 'Teaching is a system of actions involving an agent, an end in view and a situation including two sets of factors those over which the agent has no control (class size, characteristics of pupils, physical facilities, etc.) and those which he can modify (such as techniques and strategies of teaching. As I mentioned earlier, teaching, among other things, is about understanding students' needs, and for that, there is a needs analysis that has to be conducted.

1.2 Language for Specific Purposes

Language for Specific Purposes is an aspect of linguistics that totally responds to students' needs. According to some scholars, such as A. Waters (1987), D. Crystal (2003), K. Westerfield (2012), and J.A. Fishman (1965), the true movement in LSP or specialized languages began in the early 1960s¹¹. But, taking into consideration the importance given to other languages regarding, specialized language, which is minimal, English has prevailed and dominated this field of linguistics. But what led to the growth of this aspect of linguistics? In their book 'English for Specific Reasons', Hutchinson & Waters (1987)¹², list three main reasons for the emergence of ESP: the demands of a brave new world: The focus in here stands on the blooming of different areas of life such as Science, Technology, and Market. The biggest boom, and the most noticeable worldwide was that of the US be it in

economy, science or technology, which consequently, marked the development and enrichment of the mother tongue of this country, English. This leads us to the other reason which is a revolution in linguistics, specifically in the field of lexicology and terminology, by bringing in an endless number of new words and new terms. This change that occurred after WWII, but most precisely in the 1960s and continues nowadays has empowered the English language, by estimating it today as a dominant or as D. Crystal (2003)¹³ would consider it, a global language. People started to notice the importance of knowing the English Language even if they are not from countries with English as their first language. So, there started an 'era', where people had to or wanted to learn English for clear reasons, for specific purposes; a businessman wanted to expand his/her business offshore, an electrician had to know English because most of the manuals were in the English language, or just because someone wanted to learn more on his field of interest. The above-mentioned actually represents the third reason, which is the focus on the learner. ESP, is not general English where you get the fundamentals of the English language, no. Through ESP, you obtain the necessary means that will help you increase your knowledge of your field of study and make you capable of understanding and communicating with the right terminology. "ESP methodology is based on the fundamental principle that we can identify a set of core language needs of target learners and adopt teaching materials and practices that will facilitate learners to meet those needs" (Bhatia, et al., 2011, p. 3)¹⁴. When all spheres of life are either positively or negatively affected by technology, language learning, and ESP have not been spared from significant changes. This process was inevitable due to the advancements in technology and language teachers' wish to fully integrate computer and mobile phone technology in the language learning process (Warschauer & Healey, 1998)¹⁵ because the development of new technologies and language learning have always kept abreast (Vukićević-Đorđević, 2015)¹⁶. Teachers of ESP, having to actually deal with students whose needs and wants are clear, they have to be really careful and precise with the techniques and activities employed in the classroom. Specifically, integrating technology in ESP curriculum provides students with a lot of learning opportunities and advantages ranging from providing

5. ⁶ Morrison (1934), Dewey (1934). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245288.pdf>

6. ⁷ John Brubacher (1939), retrieved from <https://www.publishing.com/ESSENTIALS-OF-INSTRUCTIONAL-TECHNOLOGY-book/chapter-318-Chapter-1-TEACHING-AND-ITS-PHASES>

7. ⁸ Smith, L.A. (September 2000). Themes or motifs? Aiming for coherence through interdisciplinary outlines. *The Reading Teacher*, 54(1), 54 – 63. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245288.pdf>

8. ⁹ Gage, (1963). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245288.pdf>

9. ¹⁰ Amidon.E (1967). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245288.pdf>

10. ¹¹ D. Crystal, *English as a Global Language*, Cambridge University Press, New York, 2003.

11. ¹² Hutchinson, T., Waters, A., *English for Specific Purposes: A Learner-centered Approach*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1987

12. ¹³ D. Crystal, *English as a Global Language*, Cambridge University Press, New York, 2003.

13. ¹⁴ Bhatia V (2011) *ESP in the 21st Century: ESP Theory and Application Today*

14. ¹⁵ Warschauer, M. & Healey, D. (1998). Computers and language learning: An overview. *Language Teaching*, 31, 57-71. DOI: 10.1017/S0261444800012970

15. ¹⁶ Vukićević-Đorđević, L. (2015). Emerging technologies: Does it feel like learning? *The Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 3(3), 483-497. Retrieved from <http://espeap.junis.ni.ac.rs/index.php/espeap/article/view/263/196>

interactive and communicative activities related to their professions to tools for giving feedback and self-evaluation on that specific context (Butler-Pascoe & Wiburg, 2003).¹⁷

2. Methodology and Findings

This part of the article presents the overall design of a study conducted in the Polytechnic University of Tirana.

The study was conducted with the students of Engineering degrees, in the Polytechnic University in Tirana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering.

2.1 Participants

There are 56 students of Mechanical engineering degree, 26 students of textile engineering degree and 20 students of material engineering. The students participating in my study are mainly of age 18-21. They are mainly pre-intermediate and intermediate students.

Table 1.

Students' Data

The number of participants	102
Gender	Female, Male
Average Age	18-21
English proficiency level	Pre-intermediate, Intermediate
Nationality	Albanian
The institution where the study was conducted	Polytechnic University of Tirana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
The period when the study was conducted	October 2021- January 2022
Data collection Instrument	Questionnaire

2.2 The aim of the survey was to reveal:

- To what extent students ME are familiar with the ESP subject when they first start this course?
- To what extent technology is integrated into the learning and teaching process in the classroom?

The study investigates the background knowledge that students of the above-mentioned study programs had on the subject they were going to deal with. The program lasted 14 weeks, from October to the end of January. Throughout the semester we have been working with a method called “Mechanical Engineering”¹⁸, which covers general information regarding engineering and mechanical engineering (henceforth ME) specifically.

The book is arranged into three levels of difficulty by offering 400 vocabulary terms and phrases. The unit contains a text of entry comprehension, vocabulary, and listening skills which lead students to written and oral production activities. The text includes a variety of authentic passages, and career-specific dialogues with more than 45 readings and listening passages per Text-book lessons.

In the present study, two questionnaires were administered. The first questionnaire is conducted at the beginning of the semester while the second questionnaire is at the end of the semester.

The data were collected and analyzed from the specific context, course, and students offering the student perspective; therefore, generalizations should be avoided.

Results and findings

The aim of the first questionnaire was to reveal the familiarity of students of mechanical engineering faculty with ESP.

Even though they were aware that they would be dealing with English, most of them actually thought they would be dealing with general English and not specialized English which has in focus their own field of study.

On the other side, as it is shown on table 2. there was a percentage of students 27.45 %, out of 100%, as Rubin (1979)¹⁹ states for the “good” language learners, who set their own directions and take responsibility for their own learning, starting with some research regarding what will they be dealing with in faculty, had made some research on what the English language consists of. The above-mentioned shows also a degree of autonomy developed in these students.

Some students knew they would have an ESP subject and not General English (henceforth, GE), and then they learned that “Mechanical Engineering” is the course they will be attending. Students of the Polytechnic University of Tirana, have the right to choose among five languages, just one. Most of the students choose English. When asked why they chose to study ESP 32 students, that is 31.37 % of them, said that it helps them succeed in their future careers. This result shows that students consider ESP a very good means of getting further in their professional life. 54 students, 52.94% acknowledged the role of English as an international language when they agreed to the statement that through the English language, you have access to the information available on the internet regarding their field of study. Cantoni and Tardini (2006), state that

16. ¹⁷ Bulter-Pascoe, M. E. (2009). English for specific purposes (ESP), innovation, and technology. In T. Chiang, W. Chuang, & L. Li (Eds.), *English Education and ESP* (pp. 1-15). Taiwan: Chien University

17. ¹⁸ Charles Lloyd, James A. Fraizer “Mechanical Engineering” from *Career Paths* by Express Publishing House, 2013

19. ¹⁹ Rubin (1973). Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/33080958/Technology_in_ESP

the Internet is mainly a contemporary communication technology that has become into a massive part of people’s lives, which is reconfirmed also by these findings.
20

Table 2.

Table 3, sheds light to students’ desire and readiness to study ESP, but the fact that students deal with English technical terminology without being introduced to the Albanian equivalent first it is a problem

for 90% of the students. They express the concern of having to learn ME first, having no background knowledge in this area in Albanian. It is difficult they say, but however, they remain optimistic.

Table 3.

Findings of the questionnaire at the end of the semester.

The second questionnaire is divided in two parts. The first part is focused on the experience students had with ESP and the second one deals with what is the main concern in this paper, the use of technology in ESP and its role.

What is actually to be emphasized in the findings of the first part of the second questionnaire is the fact that students regret dealing with English only for a semester, which is about 40 hours total.

They find it really “disappointing”. This, on the other hand, shows students’ interest in learning ESP, technical English. The same question that was asked in the first questionnaire at the beginning of the course is

20. ²⁰ Book “Internet” By Lorenzo Cantoni, Stefano Tardini

also asked in the second questionnaire; whether the absence of general knowledge in Albanian was an element that actually slowed down or interfered in the process of learning mechanical English.

The answer varied, in accordance with the engineering degree of students. The answers from mechanical and material engineering were divided 50%/50%, where 31 considered it a drawback, while the others stated that it actually didn't interfere at all in the mechanical English learning process.

While textile engineering students were unanimous, and stated that the absence of general knowledge in Albanian impeded them from fully acquiring the English mechanical engineering corpus throughout the course.

When asked about the enhancement of different skills in ESP during the course, 100% answered that this subject increased English mechanical terminology.

Table 4.

Most of the students found this course contributing to developing communication skills and technical writing skills. Technical vocabulary is defined as vocabulary that has higher frequency words in specific fields such as engineering, science, and medicine (Harmon & Wood, 2018)²¹. These words have their own specific meanings that are designed specifically for certain fields (Hiebert, Scott, Castaneda, & Spichtig, 2019).²²

The second part of the questionnaire concentrated on the use of technology in the classroom by students and professors, from students' perspectives.

The feedback from the students, as far as the use of technology is concerned, showed that the only technological tools used during the ESP Course were the laptop, provided by the professor herself, smartphones, and the Internet which was present every single time. On some rare occasions, a video projector would become part of the teaching process, because unfortunately there are few classes with a video projector in them.

However, their answers reveal that, even though there are not many tools attached to the teaching and learning process in the class, many different techniques and activities are performed throughout the process by improving teaching productivity, facilitating better planning, enabling an easy and practical learning, quick and correct assessment. Students' active participation and engagement in this process positively influences their academic performance (Emerson & Taylor, 2004).²³

Throughout the semester it was noticed that most of the students had online dictionaries downloaded on their smartphones therefore they were asked about the type the dictionary, and most of the answers were: 55 % Free Online dictionaries and 15% free online technical dictionaries, while only 6 % mentioned visual dictionaries, while others had no dictionaries downloaded.

21. ²¹ Harmon, J., & Wood, K. (2018). The Vocabulary-Comprehension Relationship across the Disciplines: Implications for Instruction. *Education Sciences*, 8(3), 101.

22. ²² Hiebert, E., Scott, J., Castaneda, R., & Spichtig, A. (2019). An analysis of the features of words that influence vocabulary difficulty. *Education Sciences*, 9(1), 8

23. ²³ Emerson & Taylor, 2004. Comparing Student Achievement across Experimental and Lecture-Oriented Sections of a Principles of Microeconomics Course

Dudley-Evans (1998)²⁴ includes vocabulary as one of the absolute characteristics of ESP: "ESP is centered on the language appropriate to these activities in terms of grammar, lexis, register, study skills, discourse and genre"¹¹. This shows most of the students are aware of the crucial role vocabulary and technical terminology occupy in the ESP subject. The Internet has given rise to significant changes in language learning. The acronym ALIVE standing for the concepts of *authenticity, literacy, interaction, vitality, and empowerment* best captures the nature of these developments (Warschauer, Shetzer, and Meloni, 2000)²⁵. Students were allowed to make use of smartphones in the classroom, as well as online dictionaries. Online dictionaries enhance learners' pronunciation of new vocabulary items as well as their ability to use these items in different contexts be it in writing or speaking.

According to Prabhu (1990), there is flexibility in choosing a method to teach ESP as this relies on some factors such as teachers, students, needs analysis, etc.; any method can be chosen to be used in an ESP classroom²⁶. One of the means students of ME have been using is WhatsApp where the students and the professor discuss and exchange ideas, thoughts, or plan projects in this communication platform. "Krashen says that acquisition requires meaningful interaction in the target language - natural communication¹⁸ - in which speakers are concerned not with the form of their utterances but with the messages they are conveying and understanding" (Liu, 2015, p.142)²⁷.

Table 6, refers to students' usage of WhatsApp. Students had the right to choose more than one option.

24. ²⁴ Dudley-Evans, Tony (1998). *Developments in English for Specific Purposes: A multi-disciplinary approach*. Cambridge University Press.

25. ²⁵ Warschauer, M., Shetzer, H., & Meloni, C. (2000). *Internet for English Teaching*. Alexandria, VA: Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages.

26. ²⁶ Prabhu, Nagore. There is no best method—why? *Tesol quarterly*, 24(2), 1990, pp: 161-176.

27. ²⁷ Krashen, Stephen & Terrel, Tracy. 1983. *The natural approach: Language acquisition in the classroom*. Oxford: Pergamon Press. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342927756_A_Contribution_to_ESP_Teachers'_Training

As reported by students of ME in the questionnaire, WhatsApp has had a crucial impact on the good progress they have had from the start to the end of the course. Even though, there are different perspectives concerning the usage of social media in the learning and teaching process, some researchers (Alenazi, 2018²⁸; Bouhnik & Doshen²⁹, 2014; Chiroma, 2016; Mbukusa, 2018; Rodliyah, 2016; Yeboah & Ewur, 2014) maintained that these social media applications were not feasible, other researchers (Ajid et al., 2018³⁰; Alqasham, 2018; Asraf & Supian, 2017; Blair, 2014; Bouhnik & Doshen, 2014; Chariat, 2018; Eid & Al-Jabri, 2016; Jain et al., 2016; Lai, 2015; Mwakapina, 2016³¹; Rashid & Rahman, 2014³²; Siemens & Weller, 2011³³; Susilo, 2014; Ta'amneh, 2017³⁴) have explained how using them has been fruitful for both teachers and students.

3. Conclusions and recommendations

Through this paper, some of the ESP elements and technology integration in ESP class were observed and analyzed. As the questionnaires and the semi-structured interview were focused on students' attitudes towards

ESP and technology in the auditorium, we drew these conclusions:

1. Students of ME faculty prefer ESP subject and consider it a very important means of advancing and learning more it about their field of study.
2. The lack of background knowledge in Albanian appertaining to Mechanical Engineering, is an obstacle in the process of learning and teaching ESP, but however they remain optimistic and willing to learn the first new terms of Mechanical Engineering, in English.
3. Unfortunately, the usage of technology in class is restricted to only 2-3 technological tools.
4. Both students and teachers try to take the best out of what technology, and smartphones in particular, provide for education. WhatsApp and Online dictionaries are mobile-based sources, which contribute to the teaching and learning process. But, given the potential of technology, a sea of other platforms are available for use by educators and learners alike.

28. ²⁸ Alenazi, A. (2018). WhatsApp Messenger as a learning tool: An investigation of pre-service teachers' learning without instructor presence. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.11114/jet.v6i1.2684>

²⁹ Bouhnik, D., & Doshen, M. (2014). WhatsApp goes to school: Mobile instant messaging between teachers and students. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.28945/2051>

²⁹ ³⁰ Ajid, L. H., Reni, R., Yunita, D. U., & Dwi, S. (2018). The use of WhatsApp in collaborative learning to improve English teaching and learning process. *International Journal of Research Studies in Educational Technology*, 7(5), 29-35. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrset.2018.3004>

³⁰ ³¹ Mwakapina, Job W. (2016). WhatsApp mobile tool in second language learning: Opportunities, potentials and

challenges in higher education settings in Tanzania. *International Journal of English Language Education*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijele.v4i2.9711>

³¹ ³² Rashid, R. A., & Rahman, M. F. (2014). Social networking sites for online mentoring and creativity enhancement. *International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 6(1), 34-45. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTEL.2014.060024>

³² ³³ Siemens, G., & Weller, M. (2011). Higher education and the promises and perils of social network. *Revista de Universidad y Sociedad del Conocimiento*,

³³ ³⁴ Ta'amneh, M. A. (2017). The Effect of using WhatsApp Messenger in learning English language among university students. *International Research in Education*, 5(1), 143-151. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ire.v5i1.10801>

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